

TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION: PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS' E-LEARNING LITERACY AND COMPETENCY IN NORTH CENTRAL, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT Technology-driven education environments are evolving to meet the demands of the technological landscape worldwide. This is made possible with the shift to e-learning and, therefore, reveals the significance of teachers' e-learning literacy and competency. To that effect, this study investigates the e-learning literacy and competency of primary school teachers in North Central Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey type was adopted. The population of the study comprised all the primary school teachers in North Central Nigeria. A structured questionnaire developed by the researcher from the literature was used as an instrument for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, and a 0.76 coefficient index was obtained using the Cronbach Alpha method. The instrument was distributed across the region, and 150 primary school teachers responded to the instrument. The data collected was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Real limits were used for the interpretation of the results. The findings of the study revealed that primary school teachers have low levels of e-learning literacy and competency. There were no significant differences between the e-learning literacy levels of primary school teachers based on gender and school type. However, a significant difference was found between teachers of public and private schools' levels of e-learning competency. Therefore, it was recommended that regular training be conducted for primary school teachers in the region to improve their e-learning literacy and competency.

KEYWORDS: Technology in Education, E-learning Literacy, E-learning Competency, Primary School Teachers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology has transformed every aspect of life, including the education. This continues to drive the need to meet the educational demands in this technological revolution. Since the shift from traditional educational methods to e-learning has created technology-driven education environments, encouraging individualised-learning approach where the teacher mostly serves as a facilitator (Friyanto et al., 2021; Oladele, 2024). This approach supports customisable instruction that facilitates creativity, invention, and problem-solving skills (Oladele, 2024). Furthermore, it encourages collaboration and allows teachers to understand areas where students need improvement (Oluwatade, 2024; Disciplines, 2024). In today's class, teachers often employ e-learning resources to support their teaching processes and to empower students with requisite skills. This is especially crucial now that technology has shaped all sides of teaching and learning. The use of e-learning technologies as an educational tool opens the door to many possibilities for teaching and learning at primary schools. The possibilities are enormous, offering transformative opportunities to enhance teaching. Teaching at primary school laid the foundation for a child's education. It is the level of education that serves as the basis upon which other levels of education are built. Teachers at this level of education prepare the digital native students for life (Korkmaz & Akcay, 2024). Embracing e-learning technologies is no longer optional but a necessity, particularly at the primary school level, where teachers prepare the next generation of learners.

Studies contend that children born in this age of technological revolution have technology as an integral part of their daily activities (Imhanyehor, 2021; Korkmaz & Akcay, 2024; Oladele, 2024). Unfortunately, pupils at this level of education are mostly not using technology for learning purposes (Waycott et al., 2010; Imhanyehor, 2021; Fahm et al., 2022; Haleem et al., 2022). They use the technology for social and entertainment purposes (Anyira &

Udem, 2020; Imhanyehor, 2021). Thus, teachers play a critical role in training and guiding pupils to use technology effectively for learning. Also, equipping them with the innovative skills needed in today's technology-driven society. However, this requires teachers to possess sufficient e-learning literacy and competency, which remains a challenge in many regions, including North Central Nigeria. It is a region affected by security challenges, cultural diversity (Federal Ministry of Education, 2019), and shortage of qualified teachers (Ogunbayo and Mhlanga, 2021). The situation of primary education in North Central Nigeria is further compounded by low enrollment rates and high dropout rates, particularly in rural areas, due to poverty, child labor, and early marriages (Imhanyehor, 2021). Therefore, it is important to understand the primary school teachers' e-learning literacy and competency in preparing pupils in this technology-driven environment.

More importantly, gender and school type are some of the populous variables considered to contribute to the teachers' level of e-learning literacy and competency (Nwafor et al., 2023; Ozer & Kuloglu, 2023; Tzafilkou et al., 2023; Cheema, 2024). From the existing literature, some studies determine the e-learning literacy and competency levels of secondary school teachers, pre-service teachers, and teachers from tertiary institutions in the region and across the country with different variables. However, little was known regarding primary school teachers in North Central Nigeria. Therefore, this study fills such gap to examine the e-learning literacy and competency levels of primary school teachers in North Central Nigeria.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

E-learning offers numerous benefits, such as blending formal and informal learning environments, facilitating teamwork, and promoting self-directed or individualised learning (Albidewi & Tulb, 2014; Tigranovna, 2022; Haq et al., 2024). However, successful integration of e-learning in primary school education depends on teachers' literacy and competency. E-learning literacy refers to teachers' skills, knowledge, attitude, and readiness to interact with e-learning facilities (Hong et al., 2017; Daniel, 2018; Oluwabiyi & Chigbundu, 2023; Mohammed et al., 2024). While, e-learning competency involves teachers' ability to engage in e-learning activities (Mohammed et al., 2024). It also includes cognitive abilities such as logical reasoning, sociological abilities like adhering to ethics of using e-learning facilities, and emotional abilities such as self-motivation, self-confidence, and self-regulation in using e-learning facilities (Daniel, 2018; Oluwabiyi & Chigbundu, 2023). Studies have identified varying levels of e-learning literacy range from low (Ogunbayo & Mhlanga 2021; Imhanyehor, 2021; Marnita et al., 2023), intermediate or medium (Imhanyehor, 2021; Edeh et al., 2022; Marnita et al., 2023), and high literacy (Öçal 2017; Arslan, 2019; Shanthi & Renugadevi, 2023; Marnita et al., 2023; Korkmaz & Akeay, 2024). Similar to that of literacy, primary school teachers were found to possess low, medium, and high levels of e-learning competency (Ogunbayo & Mhlanga, 2021; Imhanyehor, 2021; Marnita et al., 2023). However, these disparities in terms of e-learning literacy and competency at the primary school level pose a great challenge as to why many teachers at this level of education struggle to engage in e-learning activities (Nwachukwu et al., 2021; Nwamaka et al., 2022).

Gender has been identified as a significant factor in e-learning literacy and competency among teachers. Some studies suggest that male primary school teachers exhibit higher levels of literacy and competency compared to their female teachers (Nwafor et al., 2023; Ozer & Kuloglu, 2023; Korkmaz & Akeay, 2024). Other studies show female primary school teachers had high digital literacy and competency levels compared to their male counterparts (Kozan, 2018; Yaman, 2019). However, in some studies, gender is not a significant factor that influences primary school teachers' digital literacy and competency (Edeh et al., 2022). Therefore, understanding gender differences in e-learning literacy and competency among primary school teachers enhances the development of training programmes that would address gender preferences (Mutambik, Lee & Almuqrin, 2020). School type is another key factor influencing e-learning literacy and competency. Studies have established that private primary school teachers have high digital literacy and competency compared to public primary school teachers (Karaferye, 2022; Shanthi & Renugadevi, 2023; Tzafilkou et al., 2023; Cheema, 2024). These differences might be a result of some public primary schools not integrating ICTs to improve teaching processes (Ogunbayo & Mhlanga, 2023). However, assessing the level of primary school teachers' e-learning literacy and competency in this technology-driven education environment is crucial. Teachers at this level of education directly deal with learners who are digital natives. Given this, this study investigated the e-learning literacy and competency of primary school teachers in North Central Nigeria, focusing on gender and school type differences.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A cross-sectional survey research design was adopted in this study. The population of this study comprised all the teachers in both public and private primary schools in North Central Nigeria. The region is comprised of seven states, including the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja. Its diverse cultural heritage influences the dynamic nature of primary education in the region. The region has introduced several initiatives that aim to provide free and compulsory education for all children (Federal Ministry of Education, 2019). This study used a multistage sampling technique to select the sample. First, the purposive sampling method was used to select only primary school teachers in North Central Nigeria. This was considered appropriate by the researcher since it allowed the targeting of a specific population that has the characteristics relevant to the objectives of the study (Palinkas et al., 2015). Quota sampling was used in the second stage to ensure various subgroups were represented within the study, using states, gender, and school type. It ensures diverse and proportional representation, which enhances the generalisability of the findings (Creswell, 2014). The respondents were 150 primary school teachers, including 53 males and 97 females. A structured questionnaire with two sub-scales was developed by the researcher, validated by three experts, and used as an instrument for data collection. The validation was done in three phases, involving construct validity, content validity, and face validity. All the observations and suggestions were affected before the production of the final copy of the instrument. The instrument was pilot tested in Northeast Nigeria, and Cronbach alpha coefficient was used to test the internal consistency. The coefficient of 0.76 was obtained which was greater than the 0.70 recommended as acceptable level (Hair et al., 2017). The following research questions guided this study:

- (a). What is the level of Primary School Teachers' e-learning literacy in North Central Nigeria?
- (b). What is the level of Primary School Teachers' e-learning Competency in North Central Nigeria?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were tested in this study at 0.05 alpha level of significance:

- (a). There is no significant difference in e-learning literacy between male and female primary school teachers in North Central Nigeria
- (b). There is no significant difference in e-learning competency between male and female primary school teachers in North Central Nigeria.
- (c). There is no significant difference in e-learning literacy between public and private primary school teachers in North Central Nigeria.
- (d). There is no significant difference in e-learning competency between public and private primary school teachers in North Central Nigeria.

The instrument was distributed online across the region. A Google Form version of the instrument was developed and distributed through primary schools, teachers, and proprietors' social media handles to the respondents. The following limits were used for the interpretation of the results. A means scores between 1.00 – 1.49 refers to; low literacy or competency, 1.50 – 2.49 refers to medium literacy or competency, and 2.50 – 3.00 refers to as high literacy or competency. Research questions were analysed using frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. The null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 alpha level of significance using an independent sample t-test.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result presented in Table 1 shows the overall grand mean of 1.27 with a standard deviation of 0.46 indicating that primary school teachers have low e-learning literacy. Looking at the items on the Table, it is interesting to note that primary school teachers have medium literacy on computers, smartphones, search engines and social media with a mean value falling between 1.50 to 2.49.

Table 1: Frequency, Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation Responses of Primary School Teachers’ E-learning Literacy

S/N	Items	I don't know this tool	I know this tool	I have the knowledge of how to use this tool	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Computer	4(2.6%)	146(97.3%)	146(97.3%)	1.63	0.21	Medium
2	Smartphones	3(2.0%)	147(98.0%)	146(97.3%)	1.63	0.19	Medium
3	Learning Management Systems like Moodle, Google Classroom, TutorNG, Canvas, etc.	12(8.0%)	138(92.0%)	83(55.3%)	1.19	0.52	Low
4	Zoom	3(2.0%)	147(98.0%)	104(69.3%)	1.35	0.47	Low
5	Google Tools (e.g. Google Meet, Form, and Sheet etc.)	7 (4.6%)	143(95.3%)	79(52.7%)	1.17	0.52	Low
6	Microsoft Team	3 (2.0%)	147(98.0%)	81(54.0%)	1.20	0.50	Low
7	E-library	4 (2.6%)	146(97.3%)	72(48.0%)	1.13	0.51	Low
8	Educational games	10 (6.6%)	140(93.3%)	64(42.7%)	1.07	0.51	Low
9	Open Educational Resources like Simulations, course modules, etc.	11 (7.3%)	139(92.7%)	65(43.3%)	1.07	0.51	Low
10	Blended Learning like flipped classroom, gamification, collaborative learning, etc.	12(8.0%)	138(92.0%)	60(40.0%)	1.04	0.52	Low
11	Search engines like Google or Ask Mama	4(2.6%)	146(97.3%)	139(92.7%)	1.58	0.28	Medium
12	Microsoft Word Application	3(2.0%)	147(98.0%)	115(76.7%)	1.43	0.52	Low
13	Microsoft PowerPoint	2(1.3%)	148(98.7%)	113(75.3%)	1.41	0.42	Low
14	Microsoft Excel	4(2.6%)	146(97.3%)	111(74.0%)	1.39	0.46	Low
15	Electronic whiteboard	4(2.6%)	146(97.3%)	80(53.3%)	1.19	0.50	Low
16	Cloud storage services (Dropbox, Google Drive, I Cloud, etc.).	9(6.0%)	141(94.0%)	80(53.3%)	1.18	0.24	Low
17	Social Media like WhatsApp, YouTube	4(2.6%)	146(97.3%)	144(96.0%)	1.61	0.51	Medium
18	Online Database	7(4.6%)	143(95.3%)	75(50.0%)	1.15	0.50	Low
19	School E-mail	3(2.0%)	147(98.0%)	80(53.3%)	1.18	0.51	Low
20	School Websites	4(2.6%)	146(97.3%)	80(53.3%)	1.19	0.52	Low
21	e-books	4(2.6%)	146(97.3%)	79(52.6%)	1.18	0.51	Low
22	Live Webinars with Q&A chats	10(6.6%)	140(93.3%)	79(52.6%)	1.16	0.53	Low
23	Digital Education Tools like Edmodo, Socrative, TED-Ed, etc.	9(6.0%)	141(94.0%)	79(52.6%)	1.17	0.52	Low
Grand Mean				1.27	0.46	Low	

From the twenty-three items presented in Table 2, the overall grand mean of 1.10 with a standard deviation of 0.46 infers that primary school teachers have low e-learning competency. Going by the items in the Table, only items 1, 11, and 17 had mean ratings within 1.50 to 2.49 with a standard deviation between 0.58 to 0.67, showing that primary school teachers had medium competency in using computers, search engines, and social media.

Table 2: Frequency, Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation Responses of Primary School Teachers’ Level of E-learning Competency

S/N	Items	I can use this tool for teaching	I have used this tool for teaching	I can fix some problems that may arise when using the tool for teaching	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Computer	146(97.3%)	123(82.0%)	106(70.6%)	1.57	0.58	Medium
2	Smartphones	104(69.3%)	94(62.6%)	83(55.3%)	1.20	0.49	Low
3	Learning Management Systems like Moodle, Google Classroom, TutorNG, Canas, etc.	83(55.3%)	83(55.3%)	70(46.6%)	1.01	0.43	Low
4	Zoom	92(61.3%)	80(53.3%)	67(44.6%)	1.00	0.37	Low
5	Google Tools (e.g. Google Meet, Form, and Sheet etc.)	79(52.6%)	75(50.0%)	74(49.3%)	1.00	0.48	Low
6	Microsoft Team	81(54.0%)	75(50.0%)	73(48.6%)	1.00	0.46	Low
7	E-library	78(52.0%)	77(51.3%)	73(48.6%)	1.00	0.47	Low
8	Educational games	87(58.0%)	75(50.0%)	74(49.3%)	1.02	0.45	Low
9	Open Educational Resources like Simulations, course modules, etc.	85(56.6%)	75(50.0%)	73(48.6%)	1.00	0.43	Low
10	Blended Learning like flipped classroom, gamification, collaborative learning, etc.	87(58.0%)	77(51.3%)	71(47.3%)	1.00	0.42	Low
11	Search engines like Google or Ask Mama	120(80.0%)	117(78.0%)	107(70.0%)	1.50	0.67	Medium
12	Microsoft Word Application	113(75.3%)	89(59.3%)	78(52.0%)	1.16	0.41	Low
13	Microsoft PowerPoint	113(75.3%)	88(58.6%)	73(48.6%)	1.12	0.36	Low
14	Microsoft Excel	111(74.0%)	79(52.6%)	63(42.0%)	1.01	0.26	Low
15	Electronic whiteboard	80(53.3%)	75(50.0%)	74(49.3%)	1.00	0.48	Low
16	Cloud storage services (Dropbox, Google Drive, I Cloud, etc.).	79(52.6%)	75(50.0%)	74(49.3%)	1.00	0.48	Low
17	Social media like WhatsApp, YouTube	127(84.7%)	117(78.0%)	107(71.3%)	1.51	0.65	Medium
18	Online Database	79(52.6%)	75(50.0%)	74(49.3%)	1.00	0.49	low
19	School E-mail	80(53.0%)	75(50.0%)	74(49.3%)	1.00	0.48	Low
20	School Websites	80(53.0%)	75(50.0%)	74(49.3%)	1.00	0.48	Low
21	E-book	79(52.6%)	75(50.0%)	74(49.3%)	1.00	0.48	Low
22	Live Webinars with Q&A chats	79(52.6%)	75(50.0%)	74(49.3%)	1.00	0.48	Low
23	Digital Education Tools like Edmodo, Socrative, TED-Ed, etc.	79(52.6%)	75(50.0%)	74(49.3%)	1.00	0.48	Low
Grand Mean Score					1.10	0.46	Low

Table 3 shows no statistically significant difference between male and female primary school teachers level of e-learning literacy in North Central Nigeria, [t(150) = 0.88, p = 0.37 > 0.05] with male teachers having ($x=1.29$ $SD=0.31$) and female teachers having ($x=1.24$, $SD=0.30$). The Table indicates that the mean scores of both male and female primary school teachers were quite close, showing that the central tendency of both groups was similar. Additionally, the standard deviation of the two groups implies that the variability within each group was also similar. The t-value of 0.88 and the p-value of 0.37 indicate that the difference in mean scores was not statistically significant and the null hypothesis was accepted.

Table 3: Independent Sample T-test of Male and Female Primary School Teachers' Level of E-learning Literacy

Category	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Df	p-value
Male	53	1.29	0.31	0.88	148	0.37
Female	97	1.24	0.30			

Table 4 revealed no statistically significant difference between male and female primary school teachers' levels of e-learning competency in North Central Nigeria [$t(148) = 1.33, p = 0.18 > 0.05$], with male teachers having ($x. = 1.16, SD=0.50$) while female teachers have ($x. = 1.04, SD=0.51$). The Table shows that the mean scores for both male and female primary school teachers were relatively different, with the male group having a higher mean score. Also, the standard deviation of the two groups implies that the variability within each group was similar. Hence, it can be said that male primary school teachers possessed a relatively high level of e-learning competency compared to their fellow female primary school teachers in North Central Nigeria. However, the t-value of 1.33 and the p-value of 0.18 showed that the difference in the mean scores was not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Table 4: Independent Sample T-test of Male and Female Primary School Teachers' Level of E-learning Competency

Gender	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Deviation	t-value	Df	p-value
Male	53	1.16	0.50	1.33	148	0.18
Female	97	1.04	0.51			

The result presented in Table 5 shows the t-value of -0.21 and the p-value of 0.82. The null hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 alpha level of significance. The null hypothesis which states that there is no statistically significant difference between the public and private primary school teachers' levels of e-learning literacy in North Central Nigeria was accepted.

Table 5: Independent Sample T-test of Public and Private Primary School Teachers' Level of E-learning Literacy

School Category	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Deviation	t-value	Df	p-value
Public	78	1.26	0.28	-0.21	148	0.82
Private	72	1.27	0.32			

As shows in Table 6, the t-value of 2.21 and the p-value of 0.02. The null hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 alpha level of significance. The null hypothesis which states that there is no statistically significant difference between the public and private primary school teachers' levels of e-learning competency in North Central Nigeria was rejected.

Table 6: Independent Sample T-test of Public and Private Primary School Teachers' Level of E-learning Competency

School Category	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Deviation	t-value	Df	p-value
Public	78	1.17	0.46	2.21	148	0.02
Private	72	0.99	0.53			

The finding on e-learning literacy as presented in this result section revealed that primary school teachers have a low level of e-learning literacy. However, it was discovered in this study that primary school teachers have a medium level of literacy in some items like computers and smartphones, with 97.3% of them agreeing to know and

have the knowledge of how to operate computers and smartphones. This inference was further sustained as 92.7% and 96.0% agreed to know and have knowledge of using search engines and social media platforms, respectively. These findings may be attributed to teachers' familiarity with integrating these technologies into their teaching activities. But it was not enough since generally their level of e-learning literacy was found to be low. This implies that efforts are still needed for teachers to be proficient in applying technologies for teaching activities. Supporting the finding of this study on the low level of primary school teachers' e-learning literacy was a study conducted by Ogunbayo and Mhlanga (2021) in some selected public primary schools in Lagos Mainland Local Education District, Lagos State, Nigeria, and found public primary school teachers with a low ICT literacy level. More so, Imhanyehor (2021) found that primary school teachers had low digital literacy in most primary schools in Benin City, Edo State. However, this low e-learning literacy of primary school teachers seems not to be only in North Central Nigeria. In Tamil Nadu, India, Shanthi and Renugadevi (2023) found that government primary school teachers had low levels of digital literacy. Contrary to the findings of this study, Oçal (2017), Ozer and Kuloglu (2023), and Korkmaz and Akcray (2024), all from different regions of Turkey, whose studies revealed that primary school teachers had high e-learning literacy.

Going by the findings of this study on gender, the low level of primary school teachers' e-learning literacy did not vary according to their gender in North Central Nigeria. This suggests that gender is not a determining factor in teachers' e-learning literacy in North Central Nigeria. This finding corroborates Kozan (2018), Yaman (2019), and Nwafor et al. (2023), whose studies found no significant difference between male and female primary school teachers' e-learning literacy. But vary with the findings of Acar (2015), Yeşildal (2018), Özerbaş and Kuralbayeva (2018), Ozer and Kuloglu (2023), and Korkmaz and Akeay (2024), whose findings revealed significant differences in e-learning literacy between male and female primary school teachers, favouring male teachers. This study equally revealed no statistically significant difference between public and private primary school teachers' e-learning literacy levels in North Central Nigeria. This shows that teachers of public and private primary schools in North Central Nigeria are of the same scale on their e-learning literacy. This finding was supported by Karaferya (2022), Shanthi and Renugadevi (2023), and Cheema (2024) in their respective findings on primary school teachers' digital literacy.

On the other hand, the findings on primary school teachers' e-learning competency indicate that primary school teachers had low levels of e-learning competency. Similar to that of e-learning literacy, it was noticed in this study that primary school teachers had medium competency on items like computers, search engines, and social media platforms. More than 70% of them indicated to some extent that they have used computers, search engines, and social media platforms and can still fix some problems that may arise while using these tools. While primary school teachers are familiar with e-learning technologies, their competency in using these tools for teaching purposes is limited. In supporting this finding, Patrick et al. (2023) found that teachers' competence in the utilisation of digitalised learning tools such as Zoom facilities, Google Classrooms, and video clips was very low. The low levels of primary school teachers' e-learning competency seem not to be an issue in North Central alone. Another study conducted in the Gandapura District of Indonesia by Marnita et al. (2023) found that public elementary schools have teachers who understand digitalisation with low, medium, and high levels of understanding.

Additionally, no statistically significant difference emerged between male and female primary school teachers' levels of e-learning competency. This finding is reinforcing that gender is not a did not have influence on teachers' e-learning competency in North Central Nigeria. This finding was supported by the findings of Nwafor et al. (2023) and Yaman (2019), whose studies found no significant difference between male and female primary teachers' e-learning competency. Unlike this study, Ozer and Kuloglu (2023) and Korkmaz and Akeay (2024) in their different studies revealed significant differences in e-learning competency between male and female primary school teachers, favouring male teachers. This study also found a significant difference between public and private primary school teachers' e-learning competency favouring public school teachers. This finding is somewhat surprising, as private schools are often assumed to have better resources and more trained teachers. However, it may reflect disparities in access to technology or differences in training opportunities between the two school types. This finding was consistent with the studies of Tzafilkou et al. (2023) and Karaferye (2022), who found a significant difference between public and private primary school teachers' e-learning competency in favour of private school teachers, unlike this study, where public primary school teachers expressed high e-learning competency.

V. CONCLUSION

This study established that the current levels of e-learning literacy and competency of primary school teachers in North Central Nigeria will reduce the chances of successful implementation of e-learning practices at primary school levels in the region. Ultimately, improving e-learning literacy and competency among primary school teachers is not just a necessity; it is a vital step toward transforming education in the region for future generations. Therefore, primary school teachers in the region must have a good level of e-learning literacy and competency to bridge the gaps in integrating e-learning technologies. This study therefore recommended regular training programs such as workshops, conferences or seminars, particularly on emerging e-learning technologies, be organised for primary school teachers in the region. This would improve their e-learning literacy and competency to actively prepare the future generation in this technology-driven society. The following are recommendations for future studies:

- (a). Future studies can consider investigating the impact of e-learning literacy and competency of primary school teachers on the students' learning outcomes in North Central Nigeria. This would help to create a direct link between teachers' e-learning literacy and competency and the students' success in the region.
- (b). Since this study investigates the primary school teachers' e-learning literacy and competency with gender, future studies can establish the role of teacher motivation and attitude on their e-learning literacy and competency.
- (c). Other studies may investigate the impact of teacher collaboration on their e-learning literacy and competency in North Central Nigeria

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REFERENCES

- [1] Acar, Ç. (2015). Anne ve babaların ilkökuller ortaokul lise öğrencisi çocukları ile kendilerinin dijital okuyazarlıklarına ilişkin görüşleri. (Master's thesis) <https://tez.yok.gov.tr>.
- [2] Albidewi, L., Tulb, R. (2014). Promise and challenges of e-learning –literature review. *European Scientific Journal*, 10(1), 210-217.
- [3] Anyira, I. E., & Udem, O. K. (2020). Effect of social media addiction on reading culture: A study of Nigerian students. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 4170.
- [4] Arslan, S. (2019). İlkokullarda ve ortaokullarda görev yapan öğretmenlerin dijital okuyazarlık düzeylerinin çeşitli değişkenler açısından incelenmesi. (Master's thesis). Sakarya University. Accessed from YÖK Thesis Center Database (Thesis No: 584170).
- [5] Bayrakçı, S. (2020). Dijital yetkinlikler bütünü olarak dijital okuyazarlık: ölçek geliştirme çalışması. (Master's thesis). Marmara University. Accessed from YÖK Thesis Center Database (Thesis No: 627541).
- [6] Cheema, J. R. (2024). Difference in literacy between private and public schools: Evidence from a survey of 61 economies. *Journal of Research in Education and Science*, 10(2), 218-240.
- [7] Chigbundu, M. C., & Oluwabiyi, M. O. (2023). Digital literacy, perception and challenges of e-learning among undergraduates in public universities of Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Multidisciplinary Studies*, 9 (11), 107-115.
- [8] Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approach* (4th ed.). SAGE publications
- [9] Daniel, S. J. (2018). E-learning literacy. Contact North, retrieved from http://empower.Eadtu.eu/images/making_sense_of_blended_learning-eng.Pdf
- [10] Disciplines (2024, December, 15). Modern trends in Nigerian educational technology. www.disciplines.ng/educational-technology-trends/
- [11] Edeh, N. C., Amedu, A. N., & Eseadi, C. (2022). Assessing Gender Differences in Teachers' Digital Literacy Skills for Assisting Students with Functional Diversity. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education (INT-JECSE)*, 14 (05), 7952-7958.
- [12] Ewa, M. A. (2024). Artificial Intelligence (AI) Literacy, an investment for enhancing educators' skills in AI-powered primary schools in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 8(4), 1226 – 1238. <https://dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2024.804093>
- [13] Fahm, A. O., Azeez, A. L., Imam-Fulani, Y. O., Mejabi, O. V., Faruk, N., Abdulrahman, M. D., Olawoyin, L. A., Oloyede, A. A., & Surajudeen-Bakinde, N. T. (2022). ICT enabled Almajiri education in Nigeria: challenges and prospects. *Education and Information Technologies*, 1-35.
- [14] Federal Ministry of Education, (2019). *National policy on education* (6th ed.) NERDC Press.
- [15] Priyanto, A., Prasetyo, I., & Albar, C. N. (2021, February). Technology-based education. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1764(1), 012193. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1764/1/012193>
- [16] Haq, A. Z., Akmansyah, M., Erlina, E., & Koderi, K. (2024). Technology integration in Arabic language learning: A literature review on the effectiveness of e-learning and mobile applications. *Journal of Research in Instructional*, 4(2), 481-494
- [17] Haleem, A., Javaid, M., Qadri, M. A., & Suman, R. (2022). Understanding the role of digital technologies in education: A review. *Sustainable Operations and Computers*, 3, 275-285.
- [18] Hong, J. C., Tai, K. H., Hwang, M. Y., Kuo, Y. C., & Chen, J. S. (2017). Internet cognitive failure is relevant to users' satisfaction with content and interface design to reflect continuance intention to use a government e-learning system. *Computers in Human Behaviour*. 66, 353-362
- [19] Imhanyehor, G. O. J. (2021). Digital literacy and primary educational system in Nigeria. *Journal of public administration, finance and law*. 10(20): 206-221
- [20] Karaferya, F. (2022). Digital teaching and learning: Exploring primary schools' approaches, sources of concern and expectations. *Journal of Educational Technology and Online Learning*. 5 (4), 808-824

- [21] Korkmaz, M., & Akcay, A. O. (2024). Determining the Digital Literacy Levels of Primary School Teachers. *Journal of Learning and Teaching in Digital Age*, 9(1): 1-16
- [22] Kozan, M. (2018). Bilgisayar ve öğretim teknolojileri eğitimi bölümü öğretmen adaylarının dijital okuryazarlık düzeyleri ve siber zorbalığa ilişkin duyarlılıklarının incelenmesi. (Master's thesis). Fırat Üniversitesi. Accessed from YÖK Thesis Center Database (Thesis No: 525797).
- [23] Marnita, Nurdin, D., & Prihatin, E. (2023). The Effectiveness of Elementary Teacher Digital Literacy Competence on Teacher Learning Management. *Journal of innovative in educational and culture research*, 4(1): 35-43. <https://jiecr.org/doi:10.46843/jecr.v4/1.444>
- [24] Mohammed, U. M., Yushau, B., Mohammed, S. A. (2024). Tertiary institution lecturers' e-learning literacy and competency in North Central Nigeria. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 5(9), 1412-1420.
- [25] Mutambik, I., Lee, J., & Almuqrin, A. (2020). Role of gender and Social Context in readiness for e-learning in Saudi high schools. *Distance Education*, 41(4), 515-539
- [26] Nwachukwu, G., Ugwu, S. and Wogu, L. (2021) Digital learning in post COVID-19 Era: Policy options and prospects for quality Education. *Nigeria in Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)* 5512
- [27] Nwafor, I. P., Ejoh, A. O., Chukwurah, M. U., & Okeke, S. U. (2023). Assessment of teachers' competence in utilization of digital instructional tools in upper basic schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. *Global journal of educational research*, 2(2): 165-175 www.globaljournalseries.com.ng
- [28] Nwamaka, O. G., Vinella, O., & Moses-Promise, O. J., (2023). ICT Competence among Secondary School Teachers during COVID-19 Pandemic: Implication for Teaching and Learning in Delta State. *Innovations*. <https://www.journal-innovations.com>
- [29] Öçal, F. N. (2017). İlkokul öğretmenleri ve velilerin kendileri ile velilerin çocuklarına ilişkin dijital okuryazarlık yeterlilik algıları (Master's thesis). Gazi Üniversitesi. Accessed from YÖK Thesis Center database (Thesis No: 450253).
- [30] Ogunbayo, S. B., & Mhlanga, N. (2022). Assessment of Public Primary School Teachers Computer Literacy and Usage in Teaching and Learning. December 2021.
- [31] Oladele, J. I. (2024). Technology readiness and implications for higher education in Universities in North-Central Nigeria. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Education Research*, 6, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.38140/ijer-2024.vol6.39>
- [32] Oluwatade, P. (2024, December, 15). The impact of technology on education in Nigeria: benefits and challenges. www.edusko.com/blog/the-impact-of-technology-on-education-in-Nigeria
- [33] Ozer, M. & Kuloglu, A. (2023). The relationship between primary school teachers' perceptions of 21st-century skills and digital literacy level. *Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 11(3):173-183.
- [34] Özerbaş, M., & ve Kuralbayeva, A. (2018). Türkiye ve Kazakistan öğretmen adaylarının dijital okuryazarlık düzeylerinin değerlendirilmesi. *Muğla Sıtkı Koçman Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 5 (1), 16-25. DOI: 10.21666/muefd.314761
- [35] Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 42(5), 533-544.
- [36] Patrick, I. N., Nwafor, A. O. E., Margaret, U. C., & Stella, U. O. (2023). Assessment of teachers' competence in utilization of digital instructional tools in upper basic schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. *Global journal of educational research*, 2(2), 165-175 www.globaljournalseries.com.ng
- [37] Prince, O. M. (2021). Addressing teaching and learning challenges amidst the COVID-19 pandemic: implication for primary schools. *International Journal on Integrated Education*
- [38] Shanthi G. & Renugadevi A. (2023) investigate the level of digital literacy amongst primary school teachers. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375794482> 9(3): 98-104
- [39] Tigranovna, M. E. (2022). Hybrid learning incorporated in higher education generates more informal learning. *Pedagogy and education*, (1), 116-125
- [40] Tunmibi, S., Aregbesola, A., Adejobi, P., & Ibrahim, O. (2015). Impact of E-Learning and Digitalization in Primary and Secondary Schools. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(17), 53-59.
- [41] Tzafilkou, K., Perifanon, M., & Economides, A. A. (2023). Assessing teachers' digital competence in primary and secondary education: applying a new instrument to integrate pedagogical and professional elements for digital education. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(5), 16017-16040
- [42] Waycott, J., Bennett, S., Kennedy, G., Dalgarno, B., and Gray, K. (2010). "Digital Divides? Student and Staff Perceptions of Information and Communication Technologies", *Computers & Education*, 54, 1202-1211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2009.11.006>
- [43] Yaman, C. (2019). Sosyal bilgiler öğretmen adaylarının dijital okuryazarlık düzeylerinin incelenmesi (Niğde Ömer Halisdemir Üniversitesi örneği). (Master's thesis). Niğde Ömer Halisdemir Üniversitesi. Accessed from YÖK Thesis Center Database (Thesis No: 555291).
- [44] Yeşildal, M. (2018). Yetişkin bireylerde dijital okuryazarlık ve sağlık okuryazarlığı arasındaki ilişki: Konya örneği. (Master's thesis). Necmettin Erbakan Üniversitesi. Accessed from YÖK Thesis Center database (Thesis No: 529488).